

Operando and *ex situ* comparison of Pt and Pt₃Co catalyst degradation under ORR in PEMFC

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. XANES analyses of the Pt₃Co catalyst in pristine conditions (*in situ*, within EC cell). Linear combination fitting results of the XANES spectra presented in Figures 1b and 1c of the main manuscript, collected from the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles in pristine conditions.

Spectra collected at the Pt L ₃ -edge		Spectra collected at the Co K-edge	
Pt ⁰	96 ± 3	Co ⁰	6 ± 2
PtO	4 ± 3	Pt ₃ Co	53 ± 3
		Co(H ₂ O) ₆ ²⁺	22 ± 5
		CoO	19 ± 3

Table S2. Complete results from the EXAFS refinements on spectra from samples in pristine conditions. Crystallographic data and structural parameters as obtained from the R-space fit by using the theoretical references.

Catalyst	Absorber	N	Atom	%	r (Å)	S ₀ ²	R-factor	σ ² (Å ²)	ΔE ₀ (eV)
Pt ^a	Pt	12 ^{a,b}	Pt	-	2.748 (3) ^a	0.57 (8) ^a	0.008 ^a	0.005 (1) ^a	8 (1) ^a
Pt ₃ Co	Pt	8 ^c	Pt	-	2.706 (9)	0.73 (9)	0.025	0.005 (4)	7.0 (1)
		4 ^c	Co	-				0.009 (*)	
	Co	12 ^c	Pt	57	2.685 (7)	0.8 (2)	0.009	0.008 (2)	-5*
		12 ^d	Co	10	2.632 (7)			0.007 (5)	
		6 ^e	O	33	2.068 (7)			0.005 (5)	

^a Reported from previous work of the same authors [1]. ^b Shell calculated from the crystallographic data of metallic Pt of Wyckoff [2]. ^c Shell calculated from the crystallographic data of Pt₃Co of Geiser and Martin [3]. ^d Shell calculated from the crystallographic data of metal Co of Häglund *et al.* [4]. ^e Shell calculated from the crystallographic data of CoO of Saito *et al.* [5]. *Fixed value

Table S3. ICP-MS. Complete ICP-MS results. Obtained from waters produced during *operando* SAXS measurements.

Catalyst	Pt/C	Pt ₃ Co	
Analyte	Pt	Pt	Co
Concentration measured during: break-in / AST (μg/L)	- / -	- / -	31.0 / -
Limit of detection (μg/L)	0.01	0.01	0.05

Table S4. XANES linear combination fitting results from spectra measured in *operando* during break-in with the Pt₃Co catalyst. Linear combination fitting results within the XANES region of the spectra collected at the Co K-edge from the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles measured in *operando* conditions (Figures 2e and 3e).

	Pristine	After break-in
Co ⁰	6 ± 1	9 ± 5
Pt ₃ Co	53 ± 2	17 ± 6
Co(H ₂ O) ₆ ²⁺	21 ± 5	56 ± 9
CoO	18 ± 3	18 ± 4

Table S5. Results of the XANES linear combination fitting analyses on data collected on *ex situ* MEAs loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst. Linear combination fitting results within the XANES region of the spectra collected from the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles measured *ex situ* at the most significant time points, selected based on *operando* electrochemical and SAXS analysis.

		Pristine	After 1250 cycles	After 2500 cycles	After 5000 cycles
Spectra collected at the Pt L ₃ -edge	Pt ⁰	93 ± 7	93 ± 9	92 ± 9	88 ± 7
	PtO	7 ± 2	7 ± 5	8 ± 6	12 ± 8
Spectra collected at the Co K-edge	Pt ₃ Co	61 ± 4	48 ± 3	68 ± 5	74 ± 5
	Co(H ₂ O) ₆ ²⁺	21 ± 5	37 ± 8	12 ± 8	4 ± 4
	CoO	18 ± 3	15 ± 2	20 ± 3	22 ± 3

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. XAS characterization in pristine conditions. (a) Spectrum of the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles measured at the Pt L₃-edge with the best linear combination fit and residual curve obtained using metallic Pt (Pt⁰) and PtO₂·H₂O. (b) Spectrum of the MEA loaded with Pt₃Co measured at the Co K-edge with the best linear combination fit and residual curve obtained using metal CoO and the spectra of Pt₃Co^(*) and Co(H₂O)₆^{2+(*)}. (c) EXAFS first shell fit on the spectrum collected on the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co nanoparticles and measured at the Pt L₃-edge. (d) Fourier-Transformed EXAFS of the Pt L₃-edge spectra of Figure 1b, collected from the MEAs hosting the Pt and Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles referred to a foil of metallic Pt; the red dashed line is used to highlight the shift to lower “ r ” values for the Pt₃Co (light blue line). Notes: ^(*) spectra from the work of Takao and co-workers [6].

Figure S2. *In operando* NAP-XPS. (a, b, c) Pt 4f and (d, e, f) Co 2p XPS spectra collected from the cathode electrode loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst. Measurements: (a,d) in pristine conditions, (b,e) by applying a constant 1.5 V potential after the break-in procedure, and (c,f) after 50 CV cycles with the potential sweeping between 1.0 and 1.5 V. Note: the Pt^{X+} represents the fraction of highly-oxidised Pt specimen which distinction is beyond the scope of this work. Pt^{Z+} represents the overall oxidised Pt fraction.

Figure S3. Pt catalyst, results of SAXS data fitting during the break-in step. Time resolved evolution of the parameters composing the analytical model used for fitting SAXS patterns recorded in *operando* represented in Figure 2a. Form factor parameters representing the catalyst nanoparticles: (a) forwarded scattering probability, I_P , (b) mean particle

diameter, D_P , and (c) standard deviation, σ_P , within the Schultz distribution; (d) calculated particle volume fraction, ϕ . Structure factor parameters: (e) fractal number, D_f , and (f) calculated radius of gyration of the fractal aggregate, R_g . Debye-Anderson-Brumberger form factor used to represent the Vulcan support: (g) forwarded scattering probability, A ; the correlation length value, ξ was kept fixed at 36.07 nm, as previously done [1,7]. Voigt peak parameters used to model the ionomer peak from Nafion electrolyte: (h) peak intensity, I_{IP} , (i) peak width, σ_{IP} , and (j) peak position, q_{IP} ; the shape factor (s_{IP}) was kept fixed at 0.45, as previously done [1,7]. Power law parameters, used to model the GDLs: (k) forwarded scattering probability, C , and (l) power law exponent, p . Note: dashed lines are guides for the eye only.

Figure S4. Pt_3Co catalyst, results of SAXS data fitting during the break-in step. Time resolved evolution of the parameters composing the analytical model used for fitting SAXS patterns recorded in *operando* represented in Figure 2c. Form factor parameters representing the catalyst nanoparticles: (a) forwarded scattering probability, I_P , (b) mean particle diameter, D_P , and (c) standard deviation, σ_P , within the Schultz distribution; (d) calculated particle volume fraction, ϕ . Debye-Anderson-Brumberger form factor used to represent the Vulcan support: (e) forwarded scattering probability, A ; the correlation length value, ξ , was kept fixed at 36.07 nm, as previously done [1,7]. Voigt peak parameters used to model the ionomer peak from Nafion electrolyte: (f) peak intensity, I_{IP} , (g) peak width, σ_{IP} , and (h) peak position, q_{IP} ; the shape factor (s_{IP}) was kept fixed at 0.45, as previously done [1,7]. Power law parameters, used to model the GDLs: (i) forwarded scattering probability, C , and (j) power law exponent, p . Note: dashed lines are guides for the eye only.

Figure S5. Pt catalyst, results of SAXS data fitting during ASTs. Time resolved evolution of the parameters composing the analytical model used for fitting SAXS patterns recoded in *operando* represented in Figure 4b. Form factor parameters representing the catalyst nanoparticles: (a) forwarded scattering probability, I_P , (b) mean particle diameter, D_P , and (c) standard deviation, σ_P , within the Schultz distribution; (d) calculated particle volume fraction, ϕ . Structure factor parameters: (e) fractal number, D_f , and (f) calculated radius of gyration of the fractal aggregate, R_g . Debye-Anderson-Brumberger form factor used to represent the Vulcan support: (g) forwarded scattering probability, A ; the correlation length value (ξ) was kept fixed at 36.07 nm, as previously done [1,7]. Voigt peak parameters used to model the ionomer peak from Nafion electrolyte: (h) peak intensity, I_{IP} , (i) peak width, σ_{IP} , and (j) peak position, q_{IP} ; the shape factor (s_{IP}) was kept fixed at 0.45, as previously done [1,7]. Power law parameters, used to model the GDLs: (k) forwarded scattering probability, C , and (l) power law exponent, p . Fill dots (\bullet) represent data retrieved from fitting SAXS patterns collected in *operando* conditions (figure 4b), while empty triangles (Δ) represent data retrieved from fitting SAXS patterns collected *ex situ* (Figure S7). Dashed lines are guides for the eye only.

Figure S6 Ex situ and operando comparison of SAXS patterns. *Operando* SAXS patterns are compared with patterns collected from twin MEAs where aging was stopped at specific time points of the AST. All MEAs were loaded with the Pt nanoparticles as cathode catalysts.

Figure S7. Pt₃Co catalyst, results of SAXS data fitting during ASTs. Time resolved evolution of the parameters composing the analytical model used for fitting SAXS patterns represented in Figure 4e. Form factor parameters representing the catalyst nanoparticles: (a) forwarded scattering probability, I_P , (b) mean particle diameter, D_P , and (c) standard deviation, σ_P , within the Schultz distribution; (d) calculated particle volume fraction, ϕ . Debye-Anderson-Brumberger form factor used to represent the Vulcan support: (e) forwarded scattering probability, A ; the correlation length value (ξ) was kept fixed at 36.07 nm, as previously done [1,7]. Voigt peak parameters used to model the ionomer peak from Nafion electrolyte: (f) peak intensity, I_{IP} , (g) peak width, σ_{IP} , and (h) peak position, q_{IP} ; the shape factor (s_{IP}) was kept fixed at 0.45, as previously done [1,7]. Power law parameters, used to model the GDLs: (i) forwarded scattering probability, C , and (j) power law exponent, p . Fill dots (\bullet) represent data retrieved from fitting SAXS patterns collected *in operando* (figure 4e), while empty triangles (Δ) represent data retrieved from fitting SAXS patterns collected *ex situ* (Figure S9). Dashed lines are guides for the eye only.

Figure S8. Ex situ and operando comparison of SAXS patterns. Operando SAXS patterns are compared with patterns collected from twin MEAs where aging was stopped at specific time points of the AST. All MEAs were loaded with the Pt₃Co nanoparticles as cathode catalysts.

Figure S9. Number-weighted particle size distribution. Time resolved evolution of number weighted size distribution (within the Schultz distribution) of (a) the bare Pt nanoparticles and (c) the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles undergoing ASTs, calculated from the results from least square fitting parameters shown in Figures 5a and 5c, respectively. Skewness of the probability distribution function (v) was further calculated for both (b) the Pt, and (d) the Pt₃Co catalyst nanoparticles. Dashed lines are guides for the eye only.

Figure S10. As collected XANES spectra at the Co K-edge on the MEA loaded with the Pt₃Co catalyst in *ex situ* conditions in transmission mode in pristine conditions and after having applied ASTs.

References

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